

Table 1. Yield and income from rice - fish farming system. Hunan, China, 1990-91.

Farming system	Yield (t/ha)			Gross return (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
	Rice	Rape	Fish			
Rice - rape (control)	13.8	1.2		2068.9	1145.0	1.24
Rice - azolla - rape	14.2	1.2		2119.2	1167.9	1.21
Rice - azolla - fish - rape	12.9	1.2	0.5	2490.8	1501.1	1.52

Table 2. Energy transformation of rice - fish farming system. Hunan, China, 1990-91.

	Rice - rape (control)	Rice - azolla - rape	Rice - azolla - fish - rape
<i>Energy input (10⁸J/ha)</i>			
Total	2274	2647.0	2739
Organic	1594	1984	2082
Inorganic	268	260	252
Commodity	413	404	404
<i>Energy output (10⁸J/ha)</i>			
Total	3774.1	4647	4626
Product	2119.9	2182.4	2092
Secondary product			69
By-product	1654.2	2465	2465
<i>Energy efficiency</i>			
Output:input	1.66	1.76	1.69
Product:inorganic	7.92	8.40	8.29
Product:commodity	5.14	5.41	5.17
Inorganic:input	0.12	0.10	0.09
Light use efficiency (%)	1.03	1.23	1.21

Productivity of rainfed rice-based cropping systems in West Bengal

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We studied the relative productivity of summer crops and their effect on wet

season (WS) rice and their residual effect on lentil *Lens culinaris* L. The rice-based cropping systems were evaluated under rainfed conditions in the subhumid tropics during 1989-91.

The soil was clayey loam with pH 6.8, 0.61% organic C, 0.062% total N, 15 kg available P, and 160 kg available K/ha.

WS rice fertilized with 0, 50, or 100 kg N/ha was transplanted after the

Effect of crops and N level on wet rice yields^a and aftereffect on lentil under rainfed condition. West Bengal, India, 1989-91.

Treatment ^b	Crop yield (t/ha)						Total		Net returns (US\$ha)
	1st crop		2d crop (rice)		3d crop (lentil)				
	Grain/fiber	Straw/stock	Grain	Straw	Grain	Stock	Grain/fiber	Straw/stock	
<i>Cropping system</i>									
Fallow - rice - lentil	0.0	0.0	1.7	2.0	1.4	2.6	3.1	4.6	312
Jute - rice - lentil	1.8	8.1	3.2	3.7	1.6	2.8	6.6	14.6	1212
Rice (d) - rice - lentil	2.5	2.7	1.6	1.8	1.3	2.3	5.4	6.8	816
Mungbean - rice - lentil	0.8	7.8	3.2	3.7	1.5	2.6	5.5	14.1	980
Sesame - rice - lentil	0.9	9.1	1.6	1.7	1.4	2.4	3.9	13.2	644
Mean	1.2	5.5	2.3	2.6	1.4	2.5	4.9	10.7	—
LSD (0.05)	0.2	1.4	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	—	—	—
<i>N level in rice (kg/ha)</i>									
0	—	—	2.0	2.4	1.4	2.4	3.4	4.8	376
50	—	—	2.3	2.5	1.4	2.6	3.7	5.1	440
100	—	—	2.6	2.9	1.5	2.6	4.1	5.5	528
Mean	—	—	2.3	2.6	1.4	2.5	3.7	5.1	—
LSD (0.05)	—	—	2.0	0.1	ns	ns	—	—	—

^aMean of 2 yr. ns = not significant. ^bRice (d) = direct seeded rice.

benefit-cost ratio. Gross return, net return, and benefit-cost ratio were highest in the rice - azolla - fish - rape farming system.

Rice - azolla - rape gave the highest energy output, output-input energy ratio, product energy-inorganic energy ratio, product energy-commodity energy ratio, and light use efficiency (Table 2). Inorganic energy-input energy ratio was lowest in rice - azolla - fish - rape system. □

harvest of a fallow check and four upland crops: jute cultivar Basudev, direct seeded rice MW 10, mungbean cultivar Pusa Baisakhi, and sesame cultivar Tilottama. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design on 8- × 2-m plots.

All summer crops were sown 2 May and harvested 31 Jul; IR36 rice was transplanted 7 Aug (25 d after seeding) at 25- × 25-cm spacing, with 4 seedlings/hill. K and P (25 kg/ha each) were applied to the rice, which was harvested 14 Nov. Lentil (B77) was broadcast 19 Nov and harvested 28 Feb. No fertilizer was used.

Grain and straw yields of rice were maximum after either jute or mungbean (see table). Results were similar for third-crop lentil grain and stock yields. Jute - rice - lentil showed the maximum crop production and net return among the 3-crop systems. The mungbean - rice - lentil sequence was second.

Grain and straw/stock yields of both rice and lentil increased as the N level increased. Net returns of rice also increased. □

Farm machinery

Development of spinning brush VLV pesticide applicator

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The spinning brush very low volume (VLV) pesticide applicator is a new low-cost system that reduces labor. It works on the principle that when the bristles of

Spinning brush VLV pesticide applicator. A. Brush atomizer. B. Main frame. C. Bevel gear. D. Chemical container. E. Nozzle. F. Deflector.

a wet brush are forcibly deflected and then allowed to bounce back swiftly, a spray of fine droplets is generated.

The pesticide applicator consists of a rotary brush atomizer mounted on the end of a shaft that passes through a pipe frame. The structure is rotated manually with a bevel gear (see figure). An air bleed system is built into the lid of a 1-liter container mounted on the frame. Chemical flows by gravity at a reasonably constant rate and drips onto the brush bristles. A sheet metal deflector generates a spray when the brush is rotated.

Characteristics of spray delivered from different pesticide applicators,^a IRRI.

Equipment	VMD (μm)	NMD (μm)	VMD/ NMD	Swath width (cm)	Droplet density	
					Mean (no./ cm^2)	CV (%)
Brush applicator	187	90	2.07	100	43.1	30.2
Micro ULVA (orange nozzle, 6 V) ^b	105	73	1.43	150	127.5	47.0
CP 15 (HC 60) ^b	90	70	1.28	60	32.9	60.1
CP 16 (Blue)	230	125	1.84	50	81.2	48.3
Tung Ho (H. cone)	200	70	2.85	50	35.5	41.0

^aMention of a commercial product is for specific information only and should not be construed as product endorsement by IRRI.

^bNozzle identification in parentheses.

Droplets from the brush applicator have a volume median diameter (VMD) of 187 μm , smaller than that of knapsack sprayers CP16 and Tung Ho but bigger than that of CP15 and Micro ULVA droplets (see table). The ratio of VMD to number median diameter (NMD) for the brush applicator was 2.07 compared with 2.85 for Tung Ho, indicating greater uniformity in droplet size from the brush.

The brush applicator had a mean droplet density of 43.1 droplets/ cm^2 (CV 30.2%), which is adequate for pesticide application.

The brush applicator applied pre- and post-emergence herbicides as well as other sprayers in replicated field trials. One application of butachlor (1.5 kg ai/ha) reduced weed intensity significantly ($P < 0.05$) from 28.5 g/m^2 in the unsprayed treatment to 5.9 g/m^2 with the brush applicator, 9.7 g/m^2 with a knapsack sprayer, and 4.6 g/m^2 with a spinning disc applicator ($\text{SE} \pm 6.98$).

Mean application rates for the brush applicator were 14.6 liters/ha for butachlor and 12.2 for 2,4-D (CV 0.7-6.1%) with the operator walking at an average speed of 0.5 m/s.

The brush applicator covers a 1-m swath on the operator's right-hand side. The empty applicator weighs about 2.2 kg.

Its operation requires less effort than a knapsack sprayer. It requires 12-15 liters of water and about 6 h to cover 1 ha, whereas a knapsack sprayer requires more than 200 liters of water and 14 h/ha when water is available at the field boundary.

The brush applicator can be fabricated in local workshops and should be marketable for about US\$20.00. A patent application has been filed in the Philippines. Blueprints are available free to interested manufacturers from IRRI's Agricultural Engineering Division. □

EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

Impact of extension contact on technology adoption

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We investigated the impact of extension contact on technology adoption in a rice-based farming system in Matara District, Sri Lanka. One hundred randomly selected rice farmers were interviewed with the use of a pretested questionnaire. An index was constructed to measure the

degree of adoption of eight innovations: modern varieties, *dapog* nursery, transplanting, chemical fertilizers, chemical weed control, chemical pest and disease control, thresher use, and stubble clearing.

Farmers were grouped into early and late adopters. Frequency of extension visits was nil/few or frequent (at least once in 2 mo). Adopter categories were then cross-tabulated with frequency of extension worker visits (see table)

Twenty-two (85%) of the early adopters received frequent extension

visits compared with 42 (57%) of the late adopters. The χ^2 test indicated a significant relationship (at 0.05 level) between frequency of extension contacts and technology adoption. This implies that with more frequent visits, farmer adoption is earlier. □

Association of extension visit frequency and farmer (n = 100) technology adoption.

Frequency of visits	Early adopters (no.)	Late adopters (no.)
Nil/few	4	32
Frequent	22	42